

Condensation of Ethyl N-Arylformimidates with Sulfonylhydrazides

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In this investigation, condensation of ethyl N-arylformimidates and aryl sulfonylhydrazides in dry pyridine has been attempted.

Ethyl N-arylformimidates (I) were prepared according to the method of Roberts and Hussein¹ by heating the corresponding aromatic amines with ethyl orthoformate in the presence of small amounts of conc. HCl.

Arylsulfonylhydrazides (II)^{2a, b} were obtained by shaking dilute aqueous solution of hydrazine hydrate with arylsulfonylchloride.

Ethyl N-arylformimidates were then condensed with arylsulfonylhydrazides in dry pyridine to give arylsulfonylimidohydrazines (III) in excellent yields :

where Ar = C₆H₅-, Cl-C₆H₄-(*o*), Cl-C₆H₄-(*m*), C₂H₅-C₆H₄-(*o*),

and Ar' = C₆H₅- or CH₃-C₆H₄-(*p*)

Basically, the mechanism of this condensation reaction is similar to that of ammonolysis of carboxylic esters^{3,4,5} and may be subject to steric⁶ and polar⁷ effects.

The structures of compounds (III) were confirmed by chemical analysis and infrared spectra which showed the presence of absorption bands of -NH(2.95-3.12μ), -C = N-(6.0-6.1μ), and -SO₂-NH(7.5μ and 8.6μ).

These compounds were found to form no complexes with transition metal ions in contrast to the acylimidohydrazines (R-C(=O)-NHNH-COR) reported by Postoviski and Vershchagina⁸. This supports the assumption that enolization of the amido group in acylimidohydrazines is responsible for their complex formation and their biological activity. Although

1. Roberts and Hussein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1950.
2. a) Curtius and Lorenzen, *J. Pr* [2] 58, 166.
b) Cremlyn and Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, Suppl. 1964, **2**, 6243.
3. Ingold "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornwell Univ. Press, Ithaca, 1953.
4. Warder, *Ber*, 1881, **14**, 1361.
5. Bender, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1626.
6. Miller *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1946; 1949, **71**, 1245; 1950, **72**, 5635; 1953, **75**, 1150.
7. Corvin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 732.
8. Postoviski and Vershchagina, *Zuhr. Obshchei. Chim.*, 1950, 2139.

the hydrogen on the nitrogen adjacent to $-\text{SO}_2-$ group in sulfonylimidohydrazines (III) is more acidic than that on the nitrogen adjacent to $-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-$ group in acylimidohydrazines, compounds (III) are unable to enolize and thus unable to form complexes. However, their biological activity has not been checked yet.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. Analysis was carried out by Alfred Bernhardt's Laboratories, Ruhr, Germany. I.R. spectra were measured by Perkin Elmer Infracord Model 137B.

Arylsulfonylimidohydrazines (III): Ethyl N-arylfornimide (0.01 mole) was added to a solution of arylsulfonylhydrazide (0.01 mole) in the least amount of dry pyridine in a 50-ml conical flask. The flask was shaken for 45 min., then left to stand overnight. The solution was diluted with cold distilled water and the flask was scratched until the oil separated was set into a semisolid mass. The product was recrystallized from absolute ethanol. Our findings are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Ar N = CH-N-NSO₂Ar'
Arylsulfonylimidohydrazines

Compd. No.	Ar	Ar'	m.p. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analysis				
						C	H	N	S	Cl
1.	C ₆ H ₅ -	C ₆ H ₅ -	121-22	80	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S	reqrs 56.72 found 56.42	4.70 4.59	15.34 15.11	11.62 11.71	
2.	C ₆ H ₄ -Cl (m)	C ₆ H ₅ -	140-41	80.6	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	reqrs 50.40 found 50.83	3.87 3.87	13.57 14.08	10.34 10.49	11.47 11.92
3.	Cl-C ₆ H ₄ - (o)	C ₆ H ₅ -	131-32	77.4	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	reqrs 50.40 found 50.27	3.86 3.71	13.57 13.50	10.34 10.43	11.47 11.34
4.	C ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ - (o)	C ₆ H ₅ -	113-15	85.9	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	reqrs 59.40 found 59.05	5.60 5.30	13.90 13.85	10.55 10.60	
5.	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (m)	C ₆ H ₅ -	137	83	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂ S	reqrs 58.13 found 58.72	5.20 5.30	14.53 13.86	11.07 10.61	
6.	C ₆ H ₅ -	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (p')	146-48	76.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S	reqrs 58.13 found 58.16	5.20 5.11	14.53 14.72	11.07 11.23	
7.	Cl-C ₆ H ₄ - (m)	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (p')	150-52	75	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	reqrs 51.93 found 51.96	4.34 4.17	12.98 12.91	9.89 10.09	10.97 10.91
8.	Cl-C ₆ H ₄ - (o)	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (p')	146-47	81	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	reqrs 51.93 found 51.99	4.34 4.16	12.98 12.46	9.89 10.09	10.97 10.82
9.	C ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄ - (o)	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (p')	123-24	79	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	reqrs 60.57 found 60.68	6.00 5.79	13.25 13.43	10.09 10.23	
10.	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (o)	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (p')	150-51	82.5	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	reqrs 59.40 found 58.89	5.61 5.50	13.86 13.87	10.56 10.56	
11.	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (m)	CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ - (p')	154-56	92.4	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S	reqrs 59.40 found 58.82	5.61 5.61	13.86 13.91	10.56 10.56	

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